

This is the space set, which goes as followed:

- The line, 0th space paired 0th space, the extra 0th space, and the outcome of another 0th space.
- The length, 1 space paired 1 space, the extra 1st space, and the outcome of another 1st space.
- The width, 2 space paired 2 space, the extra 2nd space, and the outcome of another 2nd space.
- The height, 3 space paired 3 space, the extra 3rd space, and the outcome of another 3rd space.
- The position, 4 space paired 4 space, the extra 4th space, and the outcome of another 4th space.
- The area, 5th space paired 5th space, the extra 5th space, and the outcome of another 5th space.
- The volume, 6th space paired 6th space, the extra 6th space, and the outcome of another 6th space.
- The distance, 7 space paired 7th space, the extra 7th space, and the outcome of another 7th space.
- The angle, 8 space paired 8 space, the extra 8th space, and the outcome of another 8th space.
- The rotation, 9th space paired 9th space, the extra 9th space, and the outcome of another 9th space.
- The wall, 10th space paired 10th space, the extra 10th space, and the outcome of another 10th space.
- The floor, 11th space paired 11th space, the extra 11th space, and the outcome of another 11th space.
- The ceiling, 12th space paired 12th space, the extra 12th space, and the outcome of another 12th space.

Set.